

The 6G Confidential Chronicle – Research Highlights & Updates

The CONFIDENTIAL6G project is developing tools, libraries, and architectural blueprints that enable confidential computing, privacy-preserving AI/ML, and post-quantum security in next-generation 6G networks.

In this issue, we highlight the latest research outputs, events, and technical milestones from across the consortium.

Project Objectives

- Develop quantum-resistant security enablers and confidential computing tools for 6G.
- Create GDPR-compliant methods combining secure hardware and software for AI/ML.
- Build privacy-preserving edge-cloud networking for federated learning.
- Integrate and validate solutions in 5G/6G use cases.
- Support 6G security standardisation and exploitation in Europe.

Use Cases

Aviation Predictive Maintenance:
Applying confidential AI analytics on flight data to enhance safety and reliability.

Telecom Cloud Security:
Strengthening data protection in cloud-native 6G infrastructures.

Intelligent Connected Vehicles:
Ensuring secure and privacy-preserving data exchange between vehicles, edge nodes, and cloud systems.

News & Milestones

White-paper released

The project contributed to the white paper *“Next Generation Edge: Edge Computing Architectures for Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning”*, published by the OpenInfra Foundation Edge Computing Working Group.

This document presents architectural frameworks, security & data-governance considerations, and deployment lessons for EdgeAI, all of which align with the project’s objectives.

[Read more](#)

Best Paper Award at IEEE CNS 2025

A partner in the project, Network Softwareization and Security Labs (NetsLab) at University College Dublin, received the **Best Paper Award at the IEEE Conference on Communications and Network Security (CNS) 2025** with a paper on “Securing xApps in Open RAN: A Hierarchical Approach to Authentication and Authorisation”.

The work aligns with the project’s focus on securing next-generation network components in 6G.

[Read more](#)

Research on Differential Privacy published

The project supported a publication in the Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PoPETs) (Issue 2/2025) titled **“Practical Two-party Computational Differential Privacy with Active Security”**.

The protocol provides computational differential privacy (CDP) with active adversary security in a two-party setting, supporting the project’s objectives for privacy-by-design in distributed analytics.

[Read more](#)

AI & SECURITY Webinar

Presentations and recordings now available!

Organized by:

Supported by:

Webinar: AI & Security – Presentations and Recording Now Available

The project co-organised a webinar on AI & Security (30 April 2025) together with peer SNS-JU projects.

Presentations covered federated/distributed AI privacy, AI for network resilience, and security/orchestration in 6G.

[Access the recordings and slides](#)

Ignacio Cascudo Shares CONFIDENTIAL6G Insights at CWI’s 20 Years of Cryptology Workshop

Co-funded by the European Union

IMDEA Software at the 20th Anniversary Workshop of the CWI Cryptology Group

On 15 September 2025, Ignacio Cascudo from the IMDEA Software Institute participated as an invited speaker at the *Workshop for the 20th Anniversary of the CWI Cryptology Group* in Amsterdam, the Netherlands. The event brought together leading researchers and practitioners to discuss two decades of progress in cryptology and explore new directions for secure computation, communication, and privacy technologies.

[Read more](#)

Confidential Computing & Privacy-Preserving Technologies for 6G

The project’s vision is summarised in the article *“Confidential Computing and Privacy-Preserving Technologies for 6G”*, which explains the three core pillars: Confidential Computing, Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) and Confidential Communication. It also outlines the three use-cases: predictive maintenance in aviation, telecom cloud security, and intelligent connected vehicles.

[Read more](#)

Webinar

Architecting Trust in 6G: Insights from SNS JU Projects

December 5, 2025
10:00 – 13:00 CET
(Registration Open)

Webinar: Architecting Trust in 6G

5 December 2025 | 10:00–13:00 CET

Join us for a focused **webinar exploring technical approaches to trustworthy 6G**, building on the discussions opened at the EuCNC & 6G Summit 2025 workshop on 6G trustworthiness.

Speakers from leading SNS JU projects will present practical results on:

- security orchestration
- ML-driven threat prediction
- trust evaluation
- privacy-by-design
- digital twins
- confidential computing
- cyber threat intelligence

The programme includes contributions from **RIGOROUS, ITrust6G, PRIVATEER, HORSE, MARE, CONFIDENTIAL6G, SAFE-6G** and **NATWORK**, with insights into prototypes, validation work and security-focused architectures.

Chairs: Dr Mir Ghoraiishi & Dr Rhys Miller (Gigasys Solutions)

[Register here](#)
[Programme](#)

We welcome participants from research, industry and public organisations interested in the technical foundations of trustworthy 6G.

CONFIDENTIAL6G Consortium

Keep in touch with us!

Stay updated on CONFIDENTIAL6G news, results and upcoming events.

Co-funded by the European Union

